

Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Iron(III) with N-Hydroxy-N-Phenyl-N'-o-Chlorophenyl-p-Toluamidine Hydrochloride in Presence of Thiocyanate**

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THIOCYANATE method¹ is frequently used for colorimetric determination of Iron(III) but suffers from various limitations such as stability, reproducibility, nonlinearity of Beer's law, amount of thiocyanate etc. These make its routine use difficult. Even the modified method lacks selectivity². The method³ based on the ternary complex formation of Iron(III) with N-hydroxyethylenediamine N, N', N"-triacetate is fairly selective but lacks sensitivity. N-hydroxy-N, N' diarylbenzamidines are new types of organoanalytical reagents⁴. The present paper reports the use of a newly synthesised hydroxyamidine, N-hydroxy-N-phenyl-N'-o-chlorophenyl-p-toluamidine hydrochloride (HPCPTH) which reacts with Iron(III), forming a benzene extractable orange red complex in thiocyanate medium. On this basis a simple, rapid and sensitive spectrophotometric method has been developed for the determination of microgram quantities of Iron(III). The method is highly selective as Fe(II) and almost all common ions including those which usually interfere with the parent thiocyanate method and other literature methods do not interfere.

Experimental

Apparatus: Absorbance values were measured with an ECIL UV-VIS spectrophotometer model GS-865 using 1 cm matched quartz and silica cells.

Reagents and Chemicals: All the chemicals used were of A. R. grade.

The reagent (HPCPTH) was prepared by the condensation of equimolar quantities of N-o-chlorophenyl-p-toluimidoyl chloride and N-phenylhydroxylamine in ether medium. The resulting hydrochloride was crystallised from absolute alcohol containing a few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid. (Yield 75%). Found: C, 64.55%; H, 5.04%; N, 7.60%; Calculated for C₂₀H₁₈N₂OCl₂; C, 64.3%; H, 4.8%; N, 7.506%.

A stock solution of Iron(III) was obtained by dissolving 0.5 g of pure iron wire (E. Merck, A. R.) in 1:3 nitric acid. It was boiled to expel oxides of

nitrogen and standardised gravimetrically. A 5% (w/v) solution of potassium thiocyanate was used.

Procedure: An aliquot of Iron(III) solution containing 50 µg of metal was taken in a 125 ml separatory funnel. A 2 ml of 5% (w/v) thiocyanate was added. Adjusted the acidity to 0.25-0.70 M hydrochloric acid in final dilution of 25 ml. The solution was equilibrated for 2 minutes with 25 ml of 0.1% benzene solution of HPCPTH. The orange benzene layer was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the absorbance values were measured at 460 nm against reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

The absorbance of the ternary Iron(III)-HPCPTH-SCN complex was maximum at 460-470 nm with molar absorptivity 12300 l. mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ in benzene. The reagent, under similar conditions showed negligible absorbance in the region 450-700 nm.

Beer's law was obeyed upto 4.8 ppm of Iron(III) at 460 nm and the optimum concentration range on the basis of Ringbom plot was 0.8 to 4.0 ppm of metal. The Sandell's sensitivity of the colour reaction was 0.0045 µg Iron(III) per cm². The standard deviation and the relative standard deviation of the method were found to be ± 3.75 × 10⁻³ and ± 0.85% respectively with mean absorbance 0.44 unit for 15 measurements, each containing 50 µg Iron(III)/25 ml.

Effect of Variables: The maximum colour intensity was obtained in the range of 0.25-0.70 M hydrochloric acid medium. Below 0.25 and beyond 0.70 M hydrochloric acid concentration low absorbance values were obtained and the rate of extraction decreased with increase in acidity of the aqueous phase.

Various solvents like benzene, toluene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride etc. extracted the mixed chelate. Benzene was found to be the best as the ternary complex showed high distribution ratio in it.

A 25 fold and 130 fold molar excess of HPCPTH and thiocyanate were adequate for complete extraction of Iron(III). Order of addition of reagents was not critical. Excess reagents caused no adverse effect in the determination of Iron(III). A time of two minutes was sufficient for complete extraction of the thiocyanate mixed chelate. Variation of temperature from 20° to 30° did not affect the absorbance of the coloured system. The complex was stable for at least 30 hrs at 27 ± 2°.

Composition: The composition of Iron(III)-HPCPTH-thiocyanate was determined by curve fitting method⁵. The results obtained showed the formation 1:1:2 (metal : reagent : thiocyanate) mixed complex in benzene.

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Interferences : In the determination of Iron(III) at 0.4 M hydrochloric acid the effect of diverse ions were studied as described in earlier procedure. Chloride, bromide, ammonia, urea, thiourea, phthalate, nitrate, sulphate, alkali metals, alkaline earth metals and lanthanoid elements had no interfering effect upto 2000 ppm. The tolerance limits of other ions causing an error less than 2% are shown in parenthesis (in ppm) : phosphate (1200), fluoride (1400), arsenate (1600), UO_2^{2+} , Mn^{2+} (600), Fe^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Cr^{3+} (800), Ni^{2+} (2000), Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} (1600), Zr^{4+} (400), W^{6+} (200), Mo^{6+} (15), V^{5+} (50), Al^{3+} (1200), Cu^{2+} (10), Ti^{4+} (50), La^{3+} (200).

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Morpholine-4-Carbodithioate as a Gravimetric Reagent for Indium(III)

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INDIUM(III) has been precipitated quantitatively in pH range 4.4-6.7 as morpholine-4-carbodithioate complex of composition $[(C_5H_8ONS_2)_3In]$ which can be weighed after drying at 110-120°. The effect of several diverse ions on precipitation was avoided using suitable masking agents.

Numerous organic reagents employed for the estimation of Indium(III) are described¹⁻⁶. In continuation of our investigations⁶⁻⁹ here we report the application of bidentate morpholine-4-carbodithioate as new gravimetric reagent for Indium(III) and its separation from a number of ions using ammoniacal EDTA as masking agent.

Experimental

The potassium salt of the reagent morpholine-4-carbodithioate has been prepared by treating morpholine in dry ether at 0° with carbon-disulphide and adding potassium hydroxide during four hours under vigorous stirring (Molar ratio; Morpholine : Carbon disulphide and Potassium hydroxide is 1:1:1). The crude product was recrystallised from iso-propyl alcohol. The solution of indium trichloride was prepared by usual method.

Procedure for the determination of In(III) :

An aliquot of the Indium(III) solution (0.02M) was diluted to about 150 ml with distilled water. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 5.0 by adding appropriate quantity of acetate buffer. The 1% reagent (MCDT) solution (w/v) in distilled water was then added with constant stirring. A white precipitate gradually separates out which was digested on water-bath (60-65°) for about 20 minutes. The precipitate was filtered through sintered crucible (G-4), washed with distilled water and dried at 110-120°.

Effect of foreign ions on the determination of In(III) :

To study the influence of foreign ions on gravimetric determination of In(III), a definite amount of various anions and cations (2-4 fold) were added to a definite quantity of In(III) solution prior to the addition of reagent (MCDT). The pH of the solution was adjusted to 5 - 5.5 using acetate buffer and estimations were carried out as described earlier. It was found that the ions Ba(II), Ca(II), Sr(II), Mg(II), Be(II), Al(III), Th(IV), Zr(IV), NO_3^- , CH_3COO^- , Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , citrate, tartrate do not interfere in quantitative determination of Indium(III). The ions $C_2O_4^{2-}$, PO_4^{3-} and BO_3^{3-} interfere. A mixture of ammoniacal EDTA and tartrate masked Tl(I), Co(II), Fe(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Sn(II), Fe(III), In(III) and Ga(III), therefore could not be determined in presence of each other. The ions Ag(I), Hg(II), Pb(II), Cu(II), Pd(II) and Bi(III) precipitate at the same pH range, therefore create interference in their determination. To overcome this difficulty an ammoniacal mixture of EDTA and tartrate is used as masking agent for In(III) before the precipitation of aforesaid ions. The Indium(III) can be demasked by repeated treatment with HNO_3 (dilution and evaporation) and determine Indium(III) using morpholine-4-carbodithioate after neutralizing the adhering nitric acid.

The Indium(III) complex is thermally stable upto 180°. The precipitate settles within few minutes and requires less time for digestion. The digestion above 80° yield low results. It is due to the fact that In(III) dithiocarbamate in contact with water get slightly dissolved. The negative results in estimation of indium might be due to slight solubility of the In(III) chelate. The percentage of negative error varies from -0.26 to -0.29 when the complex was heated at 50-70° (digestion